

Mapping Research Topics on the Net Interest Margin (NIM) Ratio in Sharia and Conventional Banking: VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Literature Review

Eka Wahyu Hestya Budianto, Nindi Dwi Tetria Dewi
Universitas Islam Negeri Maulana Malik Ibrahim Malang
wahyu.ala@uin-malang.ac.id

Abstract

This study aims to determine the research mapping regarding the Net Interest Margin (NIM) ratio in Islamic and Conventional Banking using a mix-method approach, namely the VOSviewer bibliometric study and literature review. Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping the distribution of journal publications around the NIM ratio; (2) mapping the results of the VOSviewer bibliometric visualization around the NIM ratio based on the number of clusters and their items; and (3) mapping research topics around the NIM ratio using a literature review study. The results showed that: (1) based on the distribution of journal publications, there were 216 journal publications regarding the NIM ratio; (2) based on the mapping of the VOSviewer bibliometric study, the network visualization results around the NIM ratio are divided into 5 clusters and 173 topic items; (3) based on the mapping of literature review studies, there are 26 topics around the influence of the NIM ratio and 35 topics about the determinants of the NIM ratio. The implications and contributions of this research are to map research topics around NIM ratios in Islamic and Conventional Banking which are often or rarely researched by researchers so that they can be a reference for subsequent researchers.

Keywords: Net Interest Margin (NIM), Bibliometrics, VOSviewer, Literature Review, Islamic and Conventional Banking

Introduction

Net Interest Margin (NIM) is an important financial ratio used to measure bank efficiency and profitability in managing funds received from customers. This ratio measures the difference between the net interest income obtained by the bank from its productive assets and the total productive assets. The use of the NIM ratio in banking has been developing for a long time and tends to be stable, because this ratio provides an accurate picture of banking financial performance. The NIM ratio can provide information about how efficient the bank is in managing funds received from customers and how much profit it can generate from its operational activities. This ratio can also be used to compare a bank's financial performance with competing banks in the market. However, the NIM ratio cannot be used separately in measuring a bank's financial performance, because there are many other factors that can influence this ratio. These factors include interest rates, asset quality, operational costs and credit growth. Therefore, in measuring a bank's financial performance, the NIM ratio must be analyzed together with other factors.

Apart from that, with technological developments and digitalization, banks' business models have also changed. Banks are starting to shift to more efficient and automated business models. This could have an impact on changes in the use of the NIM ratio as the main indicator. Some banks have even adopted new metrics such as Return on Equity (ROE) and Return on Assets (ROA) to measure their financial performance. Nevertheless, the NIM ratio remains an

important ratio in measuring banking financial performance. The banking industry still uses it to monitor their efficiency and profitability, as well as to compare their performance with competing banks. Apart from that, the NIM ratio is also used as a reference by financial regulators in monitoring bank financial performance and ensuring that these banks remain healthy and stable. In conclusion, the use of the NIM ratio in banking tends to be stable and continues to be monitored by the industry and financial regulators. Even though there are technological developments and digitalization that influence banks' business models, the NIM ratio is still one of the main indicators in measuring banking financial performance. However, the use of the NIM ratio must be analyzed together with other factors in order to provide a more accurate picture of the bank's financial performance.

Several studies have been conducted to study the factors that influence NIM and its impact on bank financial performance. First, one of the most recent studies on NIM studied the relationship between NIM, credit risk and bank profitability in Bangladesh. The research results show that NIM has a significant positive influence on bank profitability, but the influence of credit risk on this relationship is negative. Second, other research studies the influence of interest rates and asset quality on NIM in China. Research results show that interest rates and asset quality have a significant influence on NIM and bank financial performance. Third, research that examines the effect of bank capital on NIM and bank financial performance in the United Arab Emirates. The research results show that bank capital has a significant positive influence on NIM and bank financial performance. Fourth, there is also research that studies the influence of macroeconomic factors on NIM, such as inflation and economic growth, which studies the influence of inflation and economic growth on NIM in Indonesia. The research results show that inflation and economic growth have a significant positive influence on NIM. Fifth, there is also research that compares the financial performance of banks in various countries using NIM as the main indicator. The research results show that the financial performance of banks in Africa varies quite widely, depending on factors such as regulations, interest rates and political stability in each country. Overall, research on NIM in banking continues to be carried out to study the factors that influence it and its impact on bank financial performance. In future developments, research on NIM is expected to provide a more comprehensive picture of bank financial performance and its influence on the economy as a whole.

The aim of this research is to map research topics around NIM in Sharia and Conventional Banking using: (1) the VOSviewer bibliometric method to analyze and study maps of literature development in publications in a scientific field by creating a metadata network map; and (2) literature study review to analyze, identify and review articles from the accredited national journal Sinta. The difference between this research and previous research is that this research explains all research topics surrounding NIM. This can be a reference for other researchers who wish to research NIM. The implication and contribution of this research is to map research topics around the NIM ratio in Sharia and Conventional Banking which are often or rarely researched by researchers, so that they can become a reference for subsequent researchers.

Literature Review

Net Interest Margin (NIM) is the difference between the interest income received by the bank from loans given to customers, minus the interest costs paid by the bank for funds received from customers. In simpler terms, NIM is

the difference between the interest rate given by the bank to borrowers and the interest rate paid by the bank for customer deposits. NIM is used to measure profitability or net profits generated by banks from lending and fund raising activities. NIM is the main indicator of a bank's financial health, because the higher the NIM, the greater the net profit the bank can generate. Therefore, NIM is one of the factors that investors take into consideration when assessing the financial performance of a bank.

Bibliometric studies are quantitative analysis methods used to evaluate scientific publications and study trends and patterns in scientific production. Bibliometric studies use bibliographic data such as the number of publications, frequency of citations, and connection data between publications to produce information about scientific developments in a particular discipline or field. In a bibliometric study, analysis is carried out on scientific publications published within a certain time period, and certain parameters are measured such as the number of publications, frequency of citations, type of publication, and trust in the publication. Using statistical analysis tools, bibliometric studies can produce useful information about trends and patterns in scientific production, and help identify research centers or institutions that are leaders in a particular field. Bibliometric studies are widely used in various fields, such as science, technology, medicine, and social sciences. Bibliometric studies can provide invaluable information for researchers, journal editors, publishers, and research funding agencies, as well as provide greater insight into scientific developments and future trends in scientific publications.

VOSviewer is software used in bibliometric studies and social network analysis to visualize and analyze bibliographic data sets. This software was developed by the Center for Science and Technology Studies at Leiden University, Netherlands. VOSviewer can be used to analyze and visualize bibliographic data in various formats, including citation data, bibliographic data obtained from scientific databases, or data from publication websites. This software can help users to discover trends and patterns in scientific publications, identify groups of researchers or institutions working on a particular topic, and visualize collaboration networks between researchers or institutions. VOSviewer can produce scientific maps and networks in a variety of formats, including cluster maps, three-dimensional maps, and collaboration networks. The software can also perform statistical analysis, such as keyword frequency analysis and bibliometric analysis. VOSviewer has been used in various fields, such as science, technology, medicine, and social sciences. This software is very useful for researchers and librarians interested in bibliometric studies and social network analysis.

Studies literature review is a systematic process for reviewing and analyzing literature relevant to a particular topic or research question. The goal is to understand what is previously known and understood about the topic, as well as to identify knowledge gaps and unanswered research needs. A literature review study involves searching, reviewing, and synthesizing literature relevant to the research topic. General steps in a literature review study include identifying research questions or topics, selecting relevant databases, collecting and selecting literature sources, reviewing and selecting literature, and compiling a summary and synthesis of relevant literature. Literature review studies can be used in a variety of fields, including social sciences, science, engineering, and health. Literature review studies are also often carried out as part of the process of writing a thesis, dissertation or scientific article, and can be used to strengthen and support arguments or research findings. Literature

review studies have several benefits, including: helping to identify knowledge gaps in a particular field; help develop more focused and relevant research questions; help identify relevant theories and conceptual frameworks; and help develop better and more appropriate research methodologies to answer existing research questions.

Methodology

This research uses research methods with a mix-method approach, namely quantitative methods in bibliometric studies and qualitative methods in literature review studies. The research object is Net Interest Margin (NIM). The type of data used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is research journal articles on NIM in Sharia and Conventional Banking.

The source of data collection comes from search for accredited national journals, Sinta via the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garba) and Perish/Harzing software. Data analysis tools use Microsoft Excel software, Mendeley Desktop, and VOSviewer. Data collection techniques include: (1) opening Perish/Harzing software, then search for journals based on the title words category with the keywords " Net Interest Margi n " and " NIM" for the entire year period; (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) formats from all journals for which data has been collected; and (4) inserting the RIS data file into Mendeley Desktop software.

Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping the distribution of journal publications around NIM using Microsoft Excel and Mendeley Desktop based on publication year; (2) mapping bibliometric network visualization results and journal publication trends around NIM using the VOSviewer (Visualization of Similarities) algorithm software based on the number of clusters and items; and (3) mapping research topics around NIM using a literature review study.

Results and Discussion

Mapping the Distribution of Journal Publications About Net Interest Margin (NIM) in Sharia and Conventional Banking

There are 216 Microsoft Excel and Mendeley Desktops originating from the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garba) and Perish/Harzing software during the period 2009 to 202 3. The results are as follows:

Table 1. Journal publication data regarding NIM by year

Year	Number of Publications	Year	Number of Publications
2009	2	2017	20
2011	1	2018	31
2012	4	2019	16
2013	6	2020	28
2014	16	2021	30
2015	10	2022	37
2016	12	2023	3

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 201 6.

- Cluster 3, consists of 31 topic items, namely: car influence analysis, analysis technique, analytical method, autocorrelation test, independent bank, car, classical assumption test, coefficient, deposit ratio, determination, f test, financial report, form, heteroscedasticity test, hypothesis testing, ldr, loan, multicollinearity, multiple regression analysis, normality test, influence of car, persero, problem, significance, significant effect, t test, tbk, test, variable car.
- Cluster 4, consists of 26 topic items, namely: annual report, bank profitability, cost, data analysis method, dependent variable, foreign exchange, documentation, productive asset quality, level, multiple linear regression, non probability sampling, operational efficiency, population, profitability, quality, quantitative research, regression analysis, sampling method/technique, secondary data, significant negative/positive effect, spss, state, data analysis techniques.
- Cluster 5, consists of 26 topic items, namely: commercial banks, bopo, business, capital adequacy ratio, conventional commercial, credit, dpk, hypothesis test, insignificant effect, intervening variable, credit, variable nim, npl, operating income, operational costs/income, percent, performing loan, purposive sampling method, quantitative approach, research model, roa, studies on commercial banks, analysis techniques, third party funds.

Mapping Literature Review Studies around the Effect of Net Interest Margin (NIM) in Sharia and Conventional Banking

Literature review study in previous research journals, researchers found 26 influences of NIM on Sharia and Conventional Banking, namely:

(1) Capital Adequacy Ratio/CAR. CAR measures how much bank capital is needed to cover credit risk and operational risk. A high NIM can increase bank profits and ultimately increase available capital. This can have a positive impact on CAR because CAR is calculated as a percentage of capital against certain risks.

(2) Bank efficiency. Bank efficiency can be measured by the ratio of operational costs to operating income. A high NIM can reduce funding costs and ultimately increase bank efficiency. However, the effect of NIM on bank efficiency may vary from one bank to another, depending on other factors such as the structure of operational costs and the volume of operating income.

(3) Financing to Deposit Ratio/FDR. FDR measures how much funds are borrowed by banks compared to funds received from customers in the form of deposits. A high NIM can generate greater income from interest, so banks can borrow less and utilize larger deposits. This can affect the FDR, because the higher the FDR, the more funds the bank has to borrow and the higher the interest costs the bank has to pay. However, the impact of NIM on FDR also depends on other factors such as market conditions, bank business strategy, and bank interest rate policies.

(4) Financial Distress. NIM can influence the level of financial risk or financial distress faced by banks. When the NIM falls, meaning that interest income decreases and interest costs are relatively stable, this can cause profits to decrease and reduce the bank's capital adequacy. Conversely, when NIM increases, this can increase profits and bank capital adequacy, thereby reducing financial risk.

(5) Share price. NIM can also influence bank share prices. When the NIM increases, this can indicate that the bank has good risk management and the right business strategy, thereby increasing investor confidence and pushing share prices up. Conversely, when the NIM falls, this can indicate greater risk and can lower the share price.

(6) Initial Public Offering/IPO. NIM can also influence a bank's decision to conduct an IPO. If a bank has a high NIM, this can indicate that the bank has the potential to generate large profits and can attract investors' interest in buying shares in the IPO. However, if the NIM is low, the bank may be less attractive to investors and the IPO may fail.

(7) Loan to Deposit Ratio/LDR. NIM can influence LDR in banking because the higher the NIM, the greater the bank's tendency to provide credit. This is because banks will get a larger interest margin by providing credit rather than placing funds in other investment instruments. On the other hand, if the NIM is low, banks will tend to be more careful in providing credit so that the LDR will tend to be low.

(8) Non Performing Loans/NPL. NIM can also influence NPL in banks because the higher the NIM, the greater the bank's tendency to provide credit with higher risk. This can cause banks to experience higher NPLs because the greater the risk taken, the greater the possibility of debtor default.

(9) Net Profit Margin/NPM. NIM can also influence NPM in banking because the higher the NIM, the greater the profits obtained by the bank. This is because banks will get a larger interest margin by placing funds in investment instruments with higher interest rates. Conversely, if NIM is low, bank profits will also tend to be low.

(10) Company value. NIM can influence company value because this ratio provides an overview of the bank's ability to generate interest income from its productive assets. The higher the NIM, the better the bank's ability to generate interest income, which in turn can increase company value.

(11) Providing credit. NIM can influence bank decisions in providing credit. Banks can tend to provide credit to sectors that have higher interest margins to increase NIM. However, this policy may pose higher credit risks, so banks must consider these risks carefully.

(12) Net profit. NIM can also have a positive effect on bank net profit. The higher the NIM, the greater the potential net interest income generated by the bank, which in turn can increase net profit. However, keep in mind that net profit can also be influenced by other factors such as operational costs, losses on asset sales, and so on.

(13) Credit distribution. NIM can affect a bank's ability to distribute credit. The higher the NIM, the more interest income the bank receives from providing credit, so the bank can have more funds to distribute credit. However, banks must also consider credit risks that may occur when disbursing credit.

(14) SME credit distribution. NIM can also influence credit distribution to the SME sector. Because banks usually provide higher interest on SME loans, a high NIM can provide an incentive for banks to be more active in channeling credit to the SME sector.

(15) Profit growth. NIM can influence bank profit growth because the interest rate the bank receives from providing credit is one of the bank's main income factors. With a high NIM, banks can generate greater interest income and increase their net profit.

(16) Changes in profit. The higher the NIM, the greater the interest income generated by the bank, thereby increasing potential profits. However,

banks must consider higher credit risks to maintain high NIMs, as higher interest rates can lead to increased credit risk.

(17) Price Book Value/PBV. PBV measures a company's market value compared to its book value. The higher the NIM, the more likely the bank will generate higher profits, and this can increase PBV. However, if the NIM is too high and the bank has to pay higher interest to attract deposits from customers, then this can cause a decrease in PBV.

(18) Price Earning Ratio/PER. PER measures a bank's share price compared to earnings per share. The higher the NIM, the more likely the bank is to generate higher profits, and this can increase PER. However, if the NIM is too high, the bank may have to pay higher interest to attract deposits from customers, and this can cause a decrease in PER.

(19) Return On Assets/ROA. ROA measures a bank's ability to generate profits from its assets. The higher the NIM, the greater the interest income generated by the bank, thereby increasing potential profits and ROA. However, if the bank has to pay higher interest to attract deposits from customers, then this can affect ROA negatively.

(20) Return On Equity/ROE. ROE measures the profits generated by a company compared to shareholder capital. The higher the NIM, the more likely the bank is to generate higher profits, and this can increase ROE. However, if the bank has to pay higher interest to attract deposits from customers, then this can affect ROE negatively.

(21) Stock returns. Share return is the profit obtained by bank shareholders from their share investments. The higher the NIM, the greater the possibility of the bank generating higher profits, and this can increase stock returns. However, other factors such as bank dividend policies and market conditions can influence stock returns as well.

(22) Bank profitability. The higher the NIM, the greater the interest income generated by the bank, thereby increasing the bank's profit potential and profitability. However, if the bank has to pay higher interest to attract deposits from customers, then this can negatively affect the bank's profitability.

(23) Credit risk. The higher the NIM, the more likely the bank is to take higher credit risk to maintain a high NIM. This can increase credit risk for banks because higher interest rates can make it difficult for customers to repay their loans. Therefore, banks need to ensure that their credit risk remains under control even though NIM is high.

(24) Stability of the bank's financial system. NIM can affect the stability of a bank's financial system if the bank takes too high a credit risk to maintain a high NIM. High credit risk can cause losses for the bank and affect the bank's overall financial health. Therefore, banks must consider credit risks and ensure that they can maintain high NIM with controlled risks.

(25) Capital structure. Capital structure refers to the proportion between share capital and debt in a company's finances. The higher the NIM, the greater the possibility of the bank having high profits and being able to increase share capital. This can affect the bank's capital structure by increasing the proportion of share capital and reducing the proportion of debt in bank finances.

(26) Total credits. The higher the NIM, the greater the interest income generated by the bank, so the bank can expand its business by offering more credit. However, banks need to consider higher credit risks because higher interest rates can make it difficult for customers to repay their loans. Therefore, banks must consider credit risks and ensure that they can maintain high NIM with controlled risks.

Mapping Literature Review Studies around the Determinant Variable Net Interest Margin (NIM) in Sharia and Conventional Banking

Literature review study in previous research journals, researchers found 35 determinant variables for NIM in Sharia and Conventional Banking, namely:

(1) Productive assets. Productive assets are all assets generated by banks that generate interest income, such as loans, bonds and mortgages. The greater the amount of a bank's productive assets, the greater the potential interest income and can increase the Net Interest Margin (NIM). However, banks also need to ensure that credit risks are controlled and that the quality of the credit provided remains high.

(2) Operational Costs to Operational Income/BOPO. BOPO is a ratio that measures how much a bank's operational costs are compared to operating income. The higher the BOPO ratio, the greater the bank's operational costs compared to operational income, so it can reduce the Net Interest Margin (NIM) because higher costs can affect bank profits. Therefore, banks need to consider managing operational costs and increasing operational efficiency so that NIM can be maintained or increased.

(3) Covid-19. The Covid-19 pandemic can affect banking financial performance and Net Interest Margin (NIM). The impact of the pandemic may result in a decrease in interest income due to lower interest rates and an increase in credit risk due to an increase in the possibility of business failure and unemployment. However, banks can take appropriate risk mitigation actions, such as loan restructuring and providing credit to sectors that are still growing, to maintain stable financial performance and NIM.

(4) Capital Adequacy Ratio/CAR. CAR is a ratio that measures a bank's ability to meet the minimum capital requirements determined by the regulator. The higher the CAR, the greater the bank's ability to bear credit risk, which in turn can increase the bank's ability to offer lower interest rates to customers. Thus, a high CAR tends to have a positive impact on NIM in banking.

(5) Third Party Funds/DPK. DPK is funds received by banks from customers in the form of deposits and savings. The higher the TPF, the more funds available for the bank to use in operational and investment activities, which in turn can increase the bank's earning potential. However, an increase in TPF can also cause an increase in bank operational costs. Therefore, the effect of TPF on NIM in banking depends on how efficient the bank is in managing its operational costs.

(6) Debt to Equity Ratio/DER. DER is a ratio that measures how much bank debt is compared to its capital. The higher the DER, the greater the risk of bank bankruptcy and the more difficult it is for banks to obtain loans at low interest rates. Conversely, a low DER can improve a bank's reputation in the capital market, which in turn can increase investor confidence and the bank's ability to obtain loans at lower interest rates. Thus, low DER tends to have a positive impact on NIM in banking.

(7) Deposits. Deposits are an important source of funding for banking. The greater the number of deposits a bank has, the greater the bank's ability to provide loans to customers and generate interest income. However, an increase in the number of deposits can also cause an increase in bank operational costs, especially if the bank is unable to manage these funds efficiently. Thus, the effect of deposits on NIM in banking depends on how efficient the bank is in managing these funds.

(8) Income diversification. Income diversification is a strategy to reduce a bank's dependence on interest income alone and expand the bank's income sources through different products and services. Income diversification can help banks to increase their income and reduce the risk of losing income if interest rates fall. In this way, the effect of income diversification on NIM in banking is positive because it can help banks to achieve an optimal balance between interest income and non-interest income.

(9) Fee Based Income. Fee based income is income obtained by banks from administration fees, transaction fees and other costs that are not related to interest income. Fee based income can be an important source of income for banks, especially when interest rates fall. The greater the fee based income, the lower the bank's dependence on interest income alone, and the greater the bank's ability to maintain their NIM at a stable level. Therefore, the influence of fee based income on NIM in banking is positive.

(10) Foreign Ownership. Foreign Ownership refers to the ownership of bank shares by foreign investors. The higher the ownership of bank shares by foreign investors, the greater the possibility of the bank being affected by changes in foreign currency exchange rates. If the foreign currency exchange rate decreases, there will be a decrease in the value of bank assets in domestic currency. As a result, banks may face pressure on their NIMs as a decline in asset values may cause banks to incur losses and reduce their ability to provide loans at competitive interest rates.

(11) Gross Domestic Product/GDP. GDP is a measure of a country's overall economic activity and reflects the overall health of the economy. The higher GDP growth, the greater the demand for credit and the greater the bank's ability to earn interest income. Therefore, high GDP growth can help increase NIM in banks.

(12) Inflation. Inflation is an increase in the overall price of goods and services and can affect interest rates. When inflation rises, central banks tend to raise interest rates to stabilize prices and encourage savings. However, an increase in interest rates can reduce loan demand and cause banks to experience a decline in NIM. Conversely, when inflation is low, the central bank can lower interest rates, which can increase loan demand and increase NIM in banks.

(13) Bank characteristics. Security is an important factor for banks in maintaining customer trust and minimizing the risk of loss. If a bank has a good reputation in terms of security and risk management, customers will feel more comfortable saving money and using the banking services offered. This can increase the number of deposits and allow banks to offer lower interest rates on loans, which can increase their NIM.

(14) Security. Security is an important factor for banks in maintaining customer trust and minimizing the risk of loss. If a bank has a good reputation in terms of security and risk management, customers will feel more comfortable saving money and using the banking services offered. This can increase the number of deposits and allow banks to offer lower interest rates on loans, which can increase their NIM.

(15) Credit performance. Credit performance is a bank's ability to provide loans and manage credit risk. If banks have good credit performance, then they can provide loans with lower risk and lower interest rates. This can increase the number of loans provided and reduce interest costs on loans, which in turn can increase the bank's NIM.

(16) Market forces. Market forces can influence NIM in banking because they can influence competition between banks. The tighter the competition between banks, the more difficult it is for banks to increase loan interest rates or reduce deposit interest rates, so that NIM can be affected. Apart from that, market forces can also influence the volume of credit distribution and third party funds, which can affect NIM.

(17) Loan to Deposit Ratio/LDR. LDR measures how much credit a bank provides compared to deposits received from customers. A high LDR can indicate that the bank is disbursing more credit than it is receiving deposits, so the bank must seek funds from other sources, such as issuing bonds or increasing deposit interest rates, which can affect NIM. On the other hand, a low LDR can indicate that the bank relies more on third party funds to distribute credit, which can affect the NIM.

(18) Gap Management. Gap Management measures the difference between the number of assets due within a certain time period and the number of liabilities due within the same time period. If a bank has a positive gap, it means that the bank has more assets maturing within a certain time period compared to liabilities maturing within the same time period. This can affect NIM because banks have to look for funding sources to fill the gap, which can affect funding costs and NIM. On the other hand, if a bank has a negative gap, it means that the bank has more liabilities maturing within a certain time period compared to assets maturing within the same time period. This can affect NIM because banks can use these funding sources to distribute credit at higher interest rates, which can increase NIM.

(19) Non-Performing Assets. NPA is non-performing loans that are not paid within a certain period of time. The higher the NPA level at a bank, the greater the risk of default that the bank must bear. This risk will affect customer and investor confidence in bank performance, so that banks will have difficulty getting cheap funds and their financial performance will decline. As a result, NIM will decrease because it will become increasingly difficult to obtain funds at low cost.

(20) Non Performing Loans/NPL. NPL is credit that is due more than 90 days. Banks that have a high level of NPL will affect the bank's performance in generating profits. Banks will bear a higher risk of default which will affect customer and investor confidence. This will have an impact on bank share prices and a decrease in NIM because it will become increasingly difficult to get cheap funds.

(21) Exchange rate. The exchange rate affects banking performance because changes in the exchange rate can affect the business volume and financial performance of the bank. Banks that are affected by changes in exchange rates will experience exchange rate risk, which means that the profits earned by the bank will decrease because the value of the bank's assets will decrease if there is a depreciation of the country's currency. The impact of decreasing bank profits is a decrease in NIM because it is increasingly difficult to get cheap funds.

(22) Opportunity Cost. Opportunity costs are costs incurred to take a particular opportunity or decision. In the banking context, opportunity costs are related to the decision to allocate bank funds to various types of investments or loans. The greater the opportunity cost, the greater the possibility of banks charging higher interest on loans and investments, thereby increasing NIM.

(23) Credit distribution. Credit distribution is one of the main sources of income for banks. The greater the amount of credit provided by the bank, the

greater the interest income generated, thereby potentially increasing NIM. However, high-risk credit distribution can result in high levels of non-performing loans (NPL), which can reduce NIM.

(24) Products. Banking products can also affect NIM. Products that offer high interest such as deposits or investments can increase NIM, but these products can also attract customer funds from other products that produce lower interest, thereby reducing NIM. Apart from that, products that are more innovative or have higher added value can also increase NIM by attracting new customers and expanding the bank's market share.

(25) Efficiency ratio. The efficiency ratio is a ratio that shows how efficient a bank is in managing its operational costs. The lower the efficiency ratio, the more efficient the bank is in managing its operational costs, which in turn can increase NIM. This is because the fewer costs required to generate income, the greater the NIM that can be achieved.

(26) Return On Assets/ROA. ROA is a ratio that shows how effective a bank is in generating profits from the assets it owns. The higher the ROA, the more effective the bank is in generating profits from the assets it owns, which in turn can increase NIM. This is because the greater the profit generated from assets, the greater the NIM that can be achieved.

(27) Return On Equity/ROE. ROE is a ratio that shows how effective a bank is in generating profits for its shareholders. The higher the ROE, the more effective the bank is in generating profits for its shareholders, which in turn can increase NIM. This is because the greater the profit generated for shareholders, the greater the NIM that can be achieved.

(28) Return On Investment/ROI. Return on Investment (ROI) is a ratio used to measure the profitability of an investment. ROI can affect NIM in banking because banks also invest by allocating funds in the form of securities or short-term loans to other companies. If the ROI resulting from the investment is high, the bank will get additional profits which can increase the NIM. However, if the ROI is low or even negative, then the bank may experience losses on its investment and the NIM may be negatively affected.

(29) Liquidity risk. Liquidity risk is related to banks' ability to meet their financial obligations in a timely manner. Liquidity risk can affect NIM in banks because if banks experience difficulty in meeting their financial obligations, they may have to pay higher interest on loans used to meet those obligations, which can reduce NIM. Conversely, if banks have good access to liquidity resources, they can reduce their funding costs and increase NIM.

(30) Credit risk. Credit risk is related to the possibility that the party who borrows money from the bank is unable or unwilling to repay the loan. Credit risk can affect the NIM in banks because if there are many bad loans, the bank can experience significant losses which can reduce the NIM. On the other hand, if banks have a healthy loan portfolio, they can minimize the risk of losses and increase NIM.

(31) Risk aversion. Risk aversion or a bank's inability to take risks can affect NIM in banking. Banks that are too careful in providing credit can reduce loan amounts and reduce interest income, which can reduce NIM. On the other hand, banks that are too aggressive in providing credit can increase credit risk and reduce financial performance, which can reduce NIM. Therefore, it is important for banks to manage risk appropriately to ensure optimal NIM.

(32) Bank Indonesia/SBI Certificate. Bank Indonesia Certificates or SBIs are short-term investment instruments issued by Bank Indonesia. The SBI interest rate can affect NIM in banking because SBI is one source of funding for

banks. If SBI interest rates rise, bank funding costs will increase, which can reduce NIM. On the other hand, if the SBI interest rate falls, bank funding costs will decrease, which can increase NIM.

(33) Interest rates. Interest rates can also affect NIM in banking because interest rates are the main factor that determines bank interest income. If interest rates rise, bank interest income will increase, which can increase NIM. On the other hand, if interest rates fall, bank interest income will decrease, which can reduce NIM. Apart from that, interest rates can also affect demand for credit and deposits, which can affect NIM.

(34) Bank size. Bank size can influence NIM in banking because larger banks tend to have advantages in terms of portfolio diversification, increased operational efficiency, and cost savings. With broader portfolios, large banks can spread risk better, which can reduce risk handling costs and increase NIM. Additionally, large banks tend to be more efficient in terms of scale of operations, which can result in lower costs and increased NIM.

(35) Rates/fees. Tariffs or fees charged by banks to customers can affect NIM because tariffs that are too high can reduce demand from customers and reduce interest income. On the other hand, if the rates or fees are too low, then the bank may not be able to cover operational costs and generate adequate NIM.

Conclusions and Recommendations

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded as follows: first, based on mapping the distribution of journal publications regarding the Net Interest Margin (NIM) ratio in Sharia and Conventional Banking during the period 2009 to 2023 which came from the accredited national journal Sinta, there are 216 published journal articles. Second, based on VOSviewer bibliometric study mapping, the network visualization results regarding the NIM ratio in Sharia and Conventional Banking are divided into 5 clusters and 173 topic items. Cluster 1 consists of 54 topics, cluster 2 consists of 36 topics, cluster 3 consists of 31 topics, cluster 4 consists of 26 topics, and cluster 5 consists of 26 topics. Third, based on mapping studies literature review, there are 26 topics related to the influence of the NIM ratio on Sharia and Conventional Banking, namely: Capital Adequacy Ratio/CAR, bank efficiency, Financing to Deposit Ratio/FDR, Financial Distress, stock prices, Initial Public Offering/IPO, Loan to Deposit Ratio/LDR, Non Performing Loans/NPL, Net Profit Margin/NPM, company value, credit provision, net profit, credit distribution, SME credit distribution, profit growth, profit changes, Price Book Value/PBV, Price Earning Ratio/PER, Return On Assets/ROA, Return On Equity/ROE, stock returns, bank profitability, credit risk, stability of the bank's financial system, capital structure, and total credit.

Furthermore, there are 35 topics related to the determinants of the NIM ratio in Sharia and Conventional Banking, namely: productive assets, Operational Costs to Operating Income/BOPO, Covid-19, Capital Adequacy Ratio/CAR, Third Party Funds/DPK, Debt to Equity Ratio/DER, deposits, income diversification, Fee Based Income, Foreign Ownership, Gross Domestic Product/GDP, inflation, bank characteristics, security, credit performance, market power, Loan to Deposit Ratio/LDR, gap management, Non Performing Assets, Non Performing Loan/NPL, exchange rate, Opportunity Cost, credit distribution, product, efficiency ratio, Return On Asset/ROA, Return On Equity/ROE, Return On Investment/ROI, liquidity risk, credit risk, Risk aversion, Bank Indonesia/SBI Certificate, interest rates, bank size, and rates/fees.

References

- Abidin, U. A., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Third-Party Fund (DPK) in Islamic and Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117572>
- Aini, A. P. N., Salsabilla, L. Z., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Compilation of Sharia Economic Law (KHES): Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117521>
- Aini, A. P. N., Salsabilla, L. Z., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Kompilasi Hukum Ekonomi Syariah (KHES): Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10078577>
- Al-Fattah, M. F., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Islamic and Conventional Mutual Funds (Reksa Dana): Library Research and VOSviewer Bibliometrics*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117306>
- Al-Fattah, M. F., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Reksa Dana Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10078579>
- Al-Ghozy, H. R., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Musaqah on Islamic Financial Inclusion: Mapping Research Topics using Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117769>
- Amaliani, A., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Income Smoothing (Perataan Laba) pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10078569>
- Amaliani, A., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Income Smoothing on Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions: Library Research and VOSviewer Bibliometrics*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117537>
- Amin, S. M. M., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Garansi pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10077304>
- Amin, S. M. M., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Guarantees on Sharia and Conventional Financial Institutions: Mapping Research Topics using Library Research and VOSviewer Bibliometrics*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117749>
- Andresta, T., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Muamalat Indonesia: Mapping Research Topics using Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117698>
- Andresta, T., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Muamalat*

Indonesia: Studi Pustaka (Library Research).
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10077344>

- Anggreni, L. S., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *National Sharia Arbitration Agency (BASYARNAS): Mapping Research Topics using Library Research and VOSviewer Bibliometrics*.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117655>
- Baranuri, M. Y., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Ijarah on Islamic Financial Inclusion: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117783>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2022). Pemetaan Penelitian Akad Mudharabah Pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik Vosviewer Dan Literature Review. *J-EBIS (Jurnal Ekonomi Dan Bisnis Islam)*, 7(1), 43–68. <https://doi.org/10.32505/j-ebis.v7i1.3895>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2022). Pemetaan Penelitian Seputar Akad Musyarakah pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *JESI (Jurnal Ekonomi Syariah Indonesia)*, 12(1), 25–36. [https://doi.org/10.21927/jesi.2022.12\(1\).25-36](https://doi.org/10.21927/jesi.2022.12(1).25-36)
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). Bibliometric And Literature Review Of Financing Risk In Islamic Banking. *JPS (Jurnal Perbankan Syariah)*, 4(1), 79–97. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.46367/jps.v4i1.1031>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Risiko Operasional pada Industri Keuangan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Ekonomi Islam*, 14(2), 158–174. <https://doi.org/10.22236/jei.v14i2.11121>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Risiko Reputasi pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Al-Masraf: Jurnal Lembaga Keuangan Dan Perbankan*, 8(1), 94–113. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.15548/al-masraf.v8i1.425>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Seputar Risiko Kredit pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *BANCO: Jurnal Manajemen Dan Perbankan Syariah*, 5(1), 20–34. <https://doi.org/10.35905/banco.v5i1.4987>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). Research Mapping on Credit Risk in Islamic and Conventional Banking. *AL-INFAQ: Jurnal Ekonomi Islam*, 14(1), 73–86. <https://doi.org/10.32507/ajei.v14i1.1862>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2022). Research Mapping of Musyarakah Contracts in Islamic Financial Institutions: VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Literature Review. *Maliki Islamic Economics Journal*, 2(2), 76–94. <https://doi.org/10.18860/miec.v2i2.17199>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Danamon Sharia and*

- Conventional: Mapping Research Topics using Library Research.*
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117751>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Danamon Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Pustaka (Library Research).*
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10077292>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR) in Islamic and Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research.*
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117611>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Cash Ratio in Sharia and Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research.*
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117607>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) in Islamic and Conventional Banking: VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117603>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Current Ratio in Islamic and Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research.*
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117601>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Dividend Payout Ratio (DPR) in Islamic and Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research.*
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117564>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Dividend Per Share in Islamic and Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research.*
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117548>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Economic Value Added (EVA) in Islamic and Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research.*
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117545>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Financial Value Added (FVA) in Islamic and Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research.*
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117539>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Financing Risk in Islamic and Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research.*
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117292>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Jualah on Islamic Financial*

- Inclusion: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117779>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Mapping Research on the Ratio of Operating Costs to Operating Income (BOPO) in Sharia and Conventional Banking: VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117623>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Net Operating Margin (NOM) on Islamic Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117324>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Net Profit Margin (NPM) Ratio in Islamic and Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117320>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Non Performing Financing (NPF) on Islamic and Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117318>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Biaya Operasional terhadap Pendapatan Operasional (BOPO) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *JAF (Journal of Accounting and Finance)*, 7(1), 34–48. <https://doi.org/10.25124/jaf.v7i1.5995>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *JAFTA (Journal of Accounting, Finance, Taxation & Auditing)*, 4(2), 32–53. <https://doi.org/10.28932/jafta.v4i2.7650>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Dividend Per Share (DPS) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Al-Mal: Jurnal Akuntansi Dan Keuangan Islam*, 4(1), 109–126. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.24042/al-mal.v4i01.16760>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Financial Value Added (FVA) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *BJRM (Bongaya Journal of Research in Management)*, 6(2), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.37888/bjrm.v6i2>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Net Operating Margin (NOM) pada Perbankan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Ecobankers: Journal of Economy and Banking*, 4(2), 84–94. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8323115>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio On Investment (ROI) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi

- Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Kompetensi (Competence : Journal of Management Studies)*, 17(1), 66–82. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.21107/kompetensi.v17i1.20002>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Total Asset Turnover (TATO) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Jurnal Akuntansi Dan Manajemen*, 20(2), 40–53. <https://doi.org/10.36406/jam.v20i2.975>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pengaruh Book Value per Share (BVS) pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Islamic Economics and Business Review*, 2(1). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8185250>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Reputation Risk in Islamic and Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117288>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Research Mapping the Operating Profit Margin (OPM) Ratio in Sharia and Conventional Banking: VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117316>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Return On Investment (ROI) in Islamic and Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117286>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Sharf on Islamic Financial Inclusion: Mapping Research Topics using Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117759>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *The Influence of Book Value per Share (BVS) on Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117619>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Total Asset Turnover (TATO) on Islamic and Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10142629>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Working Capital Turnover (WCT) Ratio in Islamic and Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117154>
- Budianto, E. W. H., Dewi, N. D. T., & Abidin, U. A. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Dana Pihak Ketiga (DPK) Pada Perbankan Syariah Dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik Vosviewer Dan Literature Review. *Syiar Iqtishadi: Journal of Islamic Economics, Finance and Banking*, 7(1), 25–44.

<https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.35448/jiec.v7i1.19887>

- Budianto, E. W. H., Saputra, H. M. G. A., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Topik Penelitian Seputar Koperasi Jasa Keuangan Syariah (KJKS): Studi Bibliometrik VOS viewer dan Literature Review. *EL MUDHORIB: Jurnal Kajian Ekonomi Dan Perbankan Syariah*, 3(2), 131–148. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8185180>
- Cahyaningrum, D., Hariyono, H. N. M., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Guarantees/Collateral in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions: Library Research and VOSviewer Bibliometrics*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117529>
- Cahyaningrum, D., Hariyono, H. N. M., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Jaminan/Agunan pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10078573>
- Dewi, N. D. T., & Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). *The Influence of Macroeconomic Variables: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117329>
- Dewi, N. D. T., Ibad, N. N., Pratopo, G., & Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Seputar Manajemen Zakat Pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer Dan Literature Review. *Jurnal Ekonomika Dan Bisnis Islam*, 6(1), 1–20. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.26740/jekobi.v6n1.p1-20>
- Elkhori, N. E. M., Safira, W. I., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Denda pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10078519>
- Emiliani, E., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Hawala on Islamic Financial Inclusion: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117785>
- Faiz, M. W., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Safe Deposit Box pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10078581>
- Fajaryati, S., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Mega Sharia and Conventional: Mapping Research Topics using Library Research and VOSviewer Bibliometrics*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117747>
- Fajaryati, S., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Mega Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10077317>
- Farida, M., Andriani, H. L., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Subrogasi pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer*.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10078583>

- Farida, M., Andriani, H. L., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Subrogation in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions: Library Research and VOSviewer Bibliometrics*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117160>
- Fauzan, I. F. M., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank OCBC NISP Sharia and Conventional: Mapping Research Topics using Library Research and VOSviewer Bibliometrics*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117745>
- Febrian, J., & Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). *Pengaruh Pengetahuan, Kepercayaan, Produk, Pelayanan, dan Religiusitas terhadap Minat Menabung*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117278>
- Febrian, J., & Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). The Effect of Knowledge, Trust, Products, Services and Religiosity on Interest in Saving. *The 9th International Conference of Islamic Economics and Business (ICONIES 2023)*, 85–96. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037033>
- Febriyanti, R., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Panin Dubai Sharia and Conventional: Mapping Research Topics using Library Research and Bibliometrics VOSviewer*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117743>
- Febriyanti, R., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Panin Dubai Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10077588>
- Fikri, U. A., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Pembangunan Daerah (BPD) Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Pustaka (Library Research)*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10077610>
- Fikri, U. A., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Sharia and Conventional Regional Development Banks (BPD): Mapping Research Topics using Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117690>
- Gozali, M., Saputra, M. A., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *The Influence of Return On Equity (ROE) in Islamic Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117294>
- Gozali, M., Saputra, M. A., Dewi, N. D. T., & Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian seputar Variabel Determinan Return On Equity (ROE) pada Perbankan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *IDEI: Jurnal Ekonomi & Bisnis*, 4(1), 34–47. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.38076/idejeb.v4i1.151>
- Hidayat, R., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Victoria Sharia and Conventional: Mapping Research Topics using Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117712>
- Hidayat, R., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Victoria Syariah*

- dan Konvensional: Studi Pustaka (Library Research)*.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10078459>
- Ibad, N. N., Pratopo, G., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Zakah Management in Islamic Financial Institutions: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research*.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117328>
- Laksana, E. Y., Rusydi, F. N., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Sharia Supervisory Board (DPS) in Islamic Financial Institutions: Library Research and VOSviewer Bibliometrics*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117554>
- Laksana, Y. E., Rusydi, F. N., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Dewan Pengawas Syariah (DPS) pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer*.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10078565>
- Mawardi, M. I., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Sharia and Conventional National Pension Savings Bank (BTPN): Mapping Research Topics using Library Research and VOSviewer Bibliometrics*.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117662>
- Muna, R. M., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Syariah Indonesia (BSI): Mapping Research Topics using Library Research and VOSviewer Bibliometrics*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117678>
- Muna, R. M., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Syariah Indonesia (BSI): Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10078436>
- Nursaputri, D. D., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Muzara'ah on Islamic Financial Inclusion: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research*.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117767>
- Panatagama, A. R., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Wakalah on Islamic Financial Inclusion: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research*.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117755>
- Prayogi, A. H., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Permata Sharia and Conventional: Mapping Research Topics using Library Research and VOSviewer Bibliometrics*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117740>
- Prayogi, A. H., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Permata Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10077628>
- Putri, S., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Bukopin Sharia and Conventional: Mapping Research Topics using Library Research and VOSviewer Bibliometrics*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117655>

- Quadratullah, M. Q., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Murabaha on Islamic Financial Inclusion: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117771>
- Rahmawati, L., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Tabungan Negara (BTN) Sharia and Conventional: Mapping Research Topics using Library Research and VOSviewer Bibliometrics*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117670>
- Ratnasari, A. D., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Rahn (Pawn) on Islamic Financial Inclusion: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117763>
- Rofiah, A., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Wadi'ah on Islamic Financial Inclusion: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117757>
- Rofika, H., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Maybank Sharia and Conventional: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117627>
- Rofika, H., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian seputar Maybank Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Jurnal Ekonomi: Journal of Economic*, 14(1), 28–39. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.47007/jeko.v14i01.6463>
- Rohimah, W., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank CIMB Niaga Sharia and Conventional on Islamic Financial Inclusion: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117629>
- Rohimah, W., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian seputar Bank CIMB Niaga Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Jurnal Ekonomi Manajemen Perbankan*, Vol 5, No 1 (2023): JEMPER Januari-Juni, 30–40. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8185264>
- Rohmah, R. A., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *The Application of Financial Accounting Standard Statements (PSAK) in Islamic and Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117314>
- Rohmandika, M. S., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian seputar Variabel Determinan Return On Asset pada Perbankan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Eco-Iqtishodi: Jurnal Ilmiah Ekonomi Dan Keuangan Syariah*, 5(1), 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.32670/ecoiqtishodi.v5i1.3607>
- Rohmandika, M. S., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Research*

Mapping around the Determinant Variables of Return on Assets (ROA) in Islamic Banking: VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117298>

Saputra, H. M. G. A., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Sharia Financial Services Cooperatives (KJKS): Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117332>

Saputri, M. I., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Internet Banking in Islamic and Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117533>

Sufia, I., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Salam on Islamic Financial Inclusion: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117761>

Suwandini, F. K. T., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Islamic Rural Banks (BPRS): Mapping Research Topics using Library Research and VOSviewer Bibliometric.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117684>

Syarifah, H. L., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Qard on Islamic Financial Inclusion: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117765>

Ummah, F. K., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Fatwa Dewan Syariah Nasional Majelis Ulama Indonesia (DSN-MUI) pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10078567>

Wulandari, D. R., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Central Asia (BCA) Sharia and Conventional: Mapping Research Topics using Library Research and Bibliometrics VOSviewer.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117704>

Wulandari, D. R., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Central Asia (BCA) Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10075718>

Zahro, T. S., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Istisna' on Islamic Financial Inclusion: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117781>